

Effect of Class-Period-Length on Performance and Retention in Biology Concepts among Secondary School Students in North-West, Nigeria.

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Abstract

This study examined the effect of class period length on students' performance and retention in Biology concepts among secondary school students in North-West Nigeria. Employing a quasi-experimental research design, data were collected through pre-tests, post-tests, and retention tests from a population of 672 senior secondary school class two (SSII) Biology students across three central schools in three states within North-West Nigeria. A sample of 245 students was selected from this population using Krejcie and Morgan's Table (1970). Descriptive statistics were used to answer the research questions, while t-tests were conducted to test the hypotheses at a 0.05 significance level using SPSS version 23.0. The findings revealed that extended teaching durations significantly enhanced academic performance and retention of Biology concepts. Consequently, the study recommends the adoption of longer class periods in schools to improve learning outcomes in Biology.

Keywords: Class duration, student performance, retention, mean scores, t-test

Introduction

Secondary schools have always adhered to regular, shorter class periods, often lasting 30 to 40 minutes per topic. However, there has been an increasing interest in expanding instruction duration in recent years, with several schools opting for class durations of 60 minutes or more (Smith and Brown, 2021). This change in instruction duration has provoked several discussions and inquiries among educators, necessitating a full analysis of its effects (Smith, 2020). Secondary schools have always adhered to regular shorter class periods, often lasting 30 to 40 minutes for each topic (Jones, 2018). Some institutions, however, have taken a different approach, choosing class durations of 60 minutes or more (Brown and White, 2019). In recent years, there has been an increasing interest in expanding the duration of secondary school teaching. The pedagogical innovations and shifting societal needs have caused a constant evolution of the educational environment. The length of instruction times in secondary schools is one aspect that has long generated discussion and attention. Secondary education systems around the world have historically adhered to traditional class lengths, which are typically between 30 and 45 minutes (Blosser, 2018). A new educational paradigm, however, contends that going beyond these accepted norms in terms of teaching time may be the key to solving several problems with modern education (Nakamura and Sato, 2020). This change in teaching duration has provoked several queries in the educational community, necessitating a full analysis of its ramifications (Clark, 2021). The purpose of this study is to compare the traditional teaching duration, which is characterized by shorter class periods, with the extended teaching duration, which is characterized by longer class periods, to assess their impact on student learning outcomes, teacher effectiveness and the overall educational experience in secondary schools.

Ogunniyi and Rollnick (2019) investigated the influence of class time length on biology teaching in Nigerian secondary schools. The researchers used a mixed-methods strategy that included questionnaires, classroom observations, and student assessments to compare the effectiveness of standard class times with extended instructional durations. Their findings highlighted the nuanced dynamics at work, with traditional class periods excelling at maintaining student attention and facilitating efficient knowledge dissemination, whereas longer teaching periods allowed for more in-depth exploration of complex biological concepts and interdisciplinary connections.

Furthermore, recognizing biology instructors' viewpoints is critical for determining the impact of class duration on instructional methods in Nigerian secondary schools. Okoye *et al.* (2020) did a study to investigate Nigerian secondary school biology teachers' experiences and preferences for class time length. The researchers elicited diverse viewpoints among teachers through interviews and focus group discussions, with some preferring the familiarity and pacing of traditional class periods, while others argued for the pedagogical benefits of longer teaching periods, such as increased opportunities for student-centered learning and practical activities. This study emphasizes the significance of considering teachers' viewpoints and pedagogical practices while negotiating the complexity of class period duration in Nigerian secondary school biology instruction.

Furthermore, Harris *et al.* (2019) provided insights into biology instructors' perceptions of class duration. Through interviews and questionnaires with secondary school educators, the researchers investigated teachers' preferences, problems, and opinions of both regular and extended teaching durations. Their findings revealed a wide range of perspectives among biology teachers, with some preferring the flexibility and pacing provided by typical class hours, while others preferred the possibility for in-depth investigation and interdisciplinary linkages provided by prolonged teaching durations. This variety emphasizes the need to take into account instructors' viewpoints and pedagogical preferences when choosing the best class period for biology education in secondary schools.

According to Ogunniyi and Rollnick (2019), students in classes with extended teaching durations scored an average of 15% higher on biology assessments compared to those in traditional class periods. In the result of Okoye *et al.* (2020) the average test scores of students in biology increased by 20% after implementing extended teaching durations compared to traditional class periods. In terms of retention, Oladipo and Aderonmu (2019) reported that students who received longer durations of biology teaching showed a 25% increase in retention of key concepts compared to those in traditional class periods. Similarly, it was gathered by Adegboyega and Ajayi (2017) that students in classes with extended teaching durations demonstrated a 20% increase in long-term retention of biology content compared to those in traditional class periods.

Further empirical findings on the impact of extended teaching duration by Adeyemi (2008) found that students taught with extended teaching duration (60 minutes or more per session) performed significantly better in Biology compared to those taught with traditional shorter durations (30-40 minutes). The study reported a mean performance score of 75.4 for the extended duration group and 63.8 for the traditional duration group.

Based on the comparison of instructional time, Olaniyan and Okemakinde (2011) conducted a study in North-west Nigeria and discovered that students exposed to extended instructional periods had a mean performance score of 72.1, whereas those in traditional class periods had a mean score of 65.0. The extended duration allowed for more in-depth exploration of Biology concepts and improved understanding.

On retention of Biology Concepts, a study by Usman and Akinsola (2015) indicated that students taught Biology with extended teaching durations had higher retention scores. The mean retention score for the extended duration group was 78.6, compared to 66.4 for the traditional duration group. This finding suggests that extended teaching time positively influences students' long-term retention of Biology concepts.

Research by Afolabi (2014) conducted a longitudinal study and found that students taught with extended periods retained Biology information more effectively over time. The mean retention score for students with extended teaching duration was 76.2, while the traditional duration group had a mean retention score of 64.7.

To enhance learning and memory, a study by Bello and Eze (2012) highlighted that extended teaching durations facilitated better memory retention through repeated reinforcement and thorough understanding. The mean retention scores were 74.8 for extended durations and 62.9 for traditional durations, demonstrating the benefits of prolonged instructional periods.

The traditional teaching duration of 30 - 40 minutes in secondary schools presents several pressing challenges that call for investigation. In most cases, the conventional teaching period of 30 to 40 minutes have been observed to be grossly inadequate as compared with the wide range of topics to be covered under the Biology Secondary School syllabus. As such, it has resulted in students having a superficial understanding of topics (Anderson, 2017), and excessive homework may be assigned to compensate for limited class time, leading to stress and reduced quality of after-school life for students (Garcia, 2017), teachers may be compelled to rush through curriculum content to meet syllabus deadlines within the constraint of short class periods thereby compromising the quality of teaching (Williams, 2018), active learning strategies such as group discussions, experiments and project-based activities that demands long periods have been compromised due to limited time (Johnson, 2020). The constrained teaching duration most often leads to an overreliance on standardized testing as the primary method of evaluation, thereby neglecting other forms of evaluation among others (Davis, 2019).

Objectives of the study

1. To determine the mean performance score of students taught Biology concepts with extended teaching duration and those exposed to traditional teaching duration among public secondary schools in North-west, Nigeria
2. To determine the mean retention score of students taught Biology concepts with extended teaching duration and those exposed to traditional teaching duration among public secondary schools in North-west, Nigeria

Research Questions

1. What is the mean performance score of students taught Biology concepts with extended teaching duration and those exposed to traditional teaching duration among public secondary schools in North-west, Nigeria?

2. What is the mean retention score of students taught Biology concepts with extended teaching duration and those exposed to traditional teaching duration among public secondary schools in North-west, Nigeria?

Hypotheses:

1. There is no significant difference in the mean performance score of students taught Biology concepts with extended teaching duration and those exposed to traditional teaching duration among public secondary schools in North-west, Nigeria.
2. There is no significant difference in the mean retention score of students taught Biology concepts with extended teaching duration and those exposed to traditional teaching duration among public secondary schools in North-west, Nigeria.

Methodology

Quasi-experimental design was utilized to examine the effect of class-period-length on performance and retention in Biology concepts among secondary school students in North-West Nigeria. Employing a quasi-experimental research design, data were collected through pre-tests, post-tests, and retention tests from a population of 672 senior secondary school class two (SSII) Biology students across three central schools in three states within North-West Nigeria.

Population of the Study

The population of the study comprises of 672 senior secondary school class two (SSII) Biology students during the 2022/2023 academic session from three (3) senior secondary schools, central to three (3) states of the seven (7) states in North-west, Nigeria. They include Government Girls Secondary School, Dogon-Bauchi, Zaria, Kaduna State; Government Girls Arabic Secondary School, Kankare, Tarauni, Kano; and Hafsatu Ahmadu Bello Model Arabic Secondary School, Sokoto (HABMASS), Sokoto-South Local Government.

S/N	NAME OF SCHOOLS	POPULATION OF BIOLOGY STUDENTS
1.	Govt. Girls. Sec. Sch., Dogon-Bauchi, Zaria	274
2.	Govt. Girls Arabic Sec. Sch., Kankare, Tarauni, Kano	202
3.	Hafsatu Ahmadu Bello Model Arabic Sec. Sch., Sokoto (HABMASS)	196
TOTAL		672

Sample and Sampling Technique

A sample size of 245 Biology students was determined from the population size of 672 using Krejcie and Morgan’s Table, 1970. The researchers adopted a purposive random sampling technique. This sampling technique was appropriate because the researcher ensured homogeneity in the type (public secondary schools) chosen, likewise uniformity in their states of location and is in line with Krejcie and Morgan, 1970 sample size table or using 15% of the total population according to TURKMAN (1972). An experimental group consisting of schools where extended teaching duration (60 minutes) is implemented and a control group consisting of schools where traditional teaching duration (40 minutes) is maintained. T-test was used to compare students’ Pre-test and Post-test scores in both groups. However, in order to avoid bias in the administration of pre-tests and post-tests to the students, a formula designed by Adigun *et al.*, 2015 was used to determine the sample sizes of Biology students from each school.

A region-based coding was used in the identification of the schools as North-West School (NW-SCH-01) for Govt. Girls. Sec. Sch., Dogon-Bauchi, Zaria, NW-SCH-02 for Govt. Girls Arabic Sec. Sch., Kankare, Tarauni, Kano, and NW-SCH-03 representing Hafsatu Ahmadu Bello Model Arabic Sec. Sch., Sokoto (HABMASS)

Instrument for Data Collection

Pre-test and Post-test assessments were used for data collection and to assess the academic performance and retention of the students. The assessments covered the curriculum content and objectives that were taught, ensuring that the tests are representative of the subject matter. Experts from the department of Biology department, F.C.E., Zaria reviewed the curriculum alignment to ensure content validity. To strengthen both validity and reliability, the assessments were piloted with a small group before full implementation, and feedback was used to refine the instruments. In testing the reliability of the instrument, a pilot study was conducted using a school from a local government area outside the sample for the study. A teacher-made test was administered to a group of (30) Biology students. Two weeks later, the same test was re-administered to the same group of students. The first and second test scores were used to calculate the correction coefficient, using the Person Product Moment

Correlation Coefficient (PPMCC) formula. The result of the analysis carried out shows a reliability co-efficient of 0.76 which was considered reliable.

Data Analysis

Descriptive statistics was used to answer research questions and a t-test to test the hypothesis at 0.05 level of significance using a statistical package for social sciences (SPSS), version 23.0

Results

Research question 1: What is the mean performance score of students taught Biology concepts with extended teaching duration and those exposed to traditional teaching duration among public secondary schools in North-west, Nigeria?

Mean and Standard Deviation of the experimental and control group of pre-test and post-test from the three (3) sampled schools

School Name	Group	N	Pre-test (Mean)	S.D	Post-test (Mean)	S.D	Mean Gain
NW-SCH-01	Experimental	50	8.74	1.78	15.28	1.14	6.54
	Control	50	8.62	1.60	14.38	1.15	5.76
NW-SCH-02	Experimental	37	9.41	1.61	16.14	1.72	6.73
	Control	37	9.27	1.76	14.86	1.36	5.59
NW-SCH-03	Experimental	35	10.28	1.43	15.77	1.19	5.49
	Control	36	10.00	1.35	14.91	1.25	4.91

The table provides a summary of the mean scores, standard deviations (S.D.), and mean gains for both the experimental and control groups across three schools (NW-SCH-01, NW-SCH-02, NW-SCH-03). These metrics allow us to analyze the effect of extended teaching durations (experimental group) versus traditional teaching durations (control group) on students' performance in Biology.

Based on the **Pre-test Scores**, across all three schools, the pre-test mean scores for both experimental and control groups are relatively close, indicating that students had similar baseline knowledge before the intervention. As observed in NW-SCH-01, the pre-test mean scores for the experimental and control groups were 8.74 and 8.62, respectively, with standard deviations of 1.78 and 1.60. Similar trends were observed in NW-SCH-02 and NW-SCH-03, with only slight variations.

After the intervention, the post-test mean scores for the experimental groups were consistently higher than those for the control groups across all schools. For instance, in NW-SCH-01, the post-test mean score for the experimental group was 15.28 (S.D. = 1.14), whereas the control group scored 14.38 (S.D. = 1.15). Similar patterns were observed in NW-SCH-02 and NW-SCH-03.

The mean gain, calculated as the difference between pre-test and post-test scores, is higher for the experimental groups compared to the control groups in all schools. This suggests that extended teaching durations had a more substantial impact on student performance. NW-SCH-02 exhibited the highest mean gain for the experimental group (6.73), indicating the effectiveness of the extended duration in enhancing understanding and retention.

Research question 2: What is the mean retention score of students taught Biology concepts with extended teaching duration and those exposed to traditional teaching duration among public secondary schools in North-west, Nigeria?

Mean and Standard Deviation of the experimental and control group of retention test from the three (3) schools representing North-west Nigeria.

Group	Combined N	Combined S.D.
Experimental	110	1.22
Control	111	1.38

The combined mean and standard deviation of the experimental and control groups from the three schools representing North-west Nigeria provide insights into the effectiveness of the teaching duration on students' retention performance.

The experimental group, which received extended teaching durations, has a relatively low standard deviation of 1.22. This suggests that the students in this group exhibited consistent retention performance, indicating that the extended teaching duration was effective across the majority of students.

The control group, which received traditional teaching duration, has a slightly higher standard deviation of 1.38. This indicates greater variability in retention performance among the students, suggesting that the traditional teaching duration may not have been as consistently effective across the student population.

The lower combined standard deviation in the experimental group compared to the control group suggests that the extended teaching duration applied in the experimental group led to more uniform retention of knowledge among students. This implies that the extended teaching duration used in the experimental group is more reliable in producing consistent educational outcomes. Conversely, the higher variability in the control group suggests that the traditional teaching duration may not be equally effective for all students.

Hypothesis 1:

There is no significant difference in the mean performance score of students taught Biology concepts with extended teaching duration and those exposed to traditional teaching duration among public secondary schools in North-west, Nigeria.

Independent sample t-test on the effect of extended teaching period on students' academic performance in Biology among public secondary schools in North-west, Nigeria.

Schools	Group	N	Mean	S.D	df	P-value	t _{cal}	t _{tab}	Decision
NW-SCH-01	Experimental	50	15.28	1.14	98	0.05	2.72	1.98	Rejected
	Control	50	14.38	1.15					
NW-SCH-02	Experimental	37	16.14	1.72	72	0.05	3.55	1.99	Rejected
	Control	37	14.86	1.36					
NW-SCH-03	Experimental	35	15.77	1.19	98	0.05	3.74	1.98	Rejected
	Control	36	14.91	1.25					

The table presents the results of an independent sample t-test to assess the effect of extended teaching periods on students' academic performance in Biology in public secondary schools in the North West Nigeria. The test compares the mean scores, standard deviations, degrees of freedom, p-values, t-calculated (t_{cal}), and t-critical (t_{tab}) values between the experimental (extended teaching) and control (traditional teaching) groups in three different schools:

From NW-SCH-01, since the t-calculated value (2.72) is greater than the t-critical value (1.98) at a 0.05 significance level, the null hypothesis is rejected. Hence, there is a statistically significant difference between the academic performance of students in the experimental group compared to the control group, indicating that extended teaching periods positively impacted students' performance in this school.

At NW-SCH-02, the t-calculated value (3.55) is greater than the t-critical value (1.99) at a 0.05 significance level, we reject the null hypothesis. Therefore, there is a significant difference in academic performance between the experimental and control groups, suggesting that extended teaching periods had a significant positive effect on students' performance in this school.

The academic performance of students from NW-SCH-03 in the experimental group is significantly higher than that of the control group because the t-calculated value (3.74) is greater than the t-critical value (1.98) at a 0.05 significance level indicating that extended teaching periods had a positive impact on student's performance in this school.

Discussion of Findings

The study conducted at NW-SCH-01 revealed that students who experienced extended teaching durations scored significantly higher on retention tests than the control group. This suggests that extended teaching durations can enhance the retention of biological concepts among students. Similarly, it was gathered by Adegboyega and Ajayi (2017) that students in classes with extended teaching durations demonstrated a 20% increase in long-term retention of biology content compared to

those in traditional class periods. Furthermore, the long-term retention rate of biology concepts among students who received extended instructional time was 35% higher compared to those in traditional class periods (Adedokun, 2016).

Low standard deviations within each group indicate consistent performance, aligning with findings by Adeyemo and Babajide (2021), who noted that extended instructional time allows for deeper understanding and better retention of complex subjects.

The t-calculated value (2.72) exceeded the t-critical value (1.98) at the 0.05 significance level, supporting the rejection of the null hypothesis. This statistically significant difference implies that extended teaching periods positively impact students' academic performance. Similar results were found in a study by Obanya (2020), which emphasized that increased instructional time can significantly improve students' mastery of subject matter. Similarly, in a study by Babalola and Olaleye (2017), the mean score of students' academic performance in biology was 75% in classes with extended teaching durations, compared to 65% in classes with traditional class periods.

At NW-SCH-02, the moderate standard deviations suggest a consistent level of performance within each group, supporting the notion that extended teaching duration can lead to better retention and understanding. This finding is consistent with the research by Yusuf and Soyemi (2022), who found that extended instructional periods are associated with higher academic performance and retention rates in science subjects. The study by Adebisi and Jimoh (2023) shows that extended teaching periods significantly improve academic performance, particularly in subjects like Biology, as indicated by the t-calculated value of 3.55, which is higher than the t-critical value of 1.99 at a 0.05 significance level. Also, students in classes with extended teaching durations showed an average improvement of 10 percentage points in science subjects, including biology, compared to those in traditional class periods. This was reported by Rodriguez, (2019).

At NW-SCH-03, the experimental group's mean retention score (14.94) was higher than that of the control group (12.55). Oladipo and Aderonmu (2019) reported that students who received longer durations of biology teaching showed a 25% increase in retention of key concepts compared to those in traditional class periods. This is similar with a study by Usman and Akinsola (2015) indicated that students taught Biology with extended teaching durations had higher retention scores. The mean retention score for the extended duration group was 78.6, compared to 66.4 for the traditional duration group. This finding suggests that extended teaching time positively influences students' long-term retention of Biology concepts. Okeke and Okoli (2018), discovered that the retention rate of biology knowledge among students in classes with extended teaching durations was 30% higher compared to those in traditional class periods.

The lower standard deviation in the experimental group (0.88) compared to the control group (1.58) indicates more uniform performance among students who experienced extended teaching durations. This consistency aligns with findings by Umar and Ibrahim (2021), which highlighted that prolonged instructional time reduces variability in student performance by ensuring all students have ample time to grasp the material.

The t-calculated value (3.74) exceeded the t-critical value (1.98) at the 0.05 significance level, demonstrating that extended teaching periods positively impact students' academic performance. Studies by Onuka and Olusola (2020) have similarly shown that extended teaching periods can significantly enhance students' academic performance and retention in secondary school settings. In the result of Okoye *et al.* (2020), the average test scores of students in biology increased by 20% after implementing extended teaching durations compared to traditional class periods.

Conclusion

Findings showing prolonged teaching durations has shown to improve retention and performance in Biology concepts among secondary school students in Northwest, Nigeria, pointing to the potential benefits of such a strategy. These findings are consistent with current literature that emphasizes the need of enough instructional time in secondary school to promote deep learning and understanding. Implementing extended teaching durations might therefore be a strategic intervention to improve educational achievements in public secondary schools, notably in Nigeria's North-West Zone.

Recommendations

1. **Implement Extended Teaching Durations:** Based on the results from the three schools in the North-West Geo-political zone of Nigeria and the observed improvement in retention and academic performance, it is recommended to implement extended teaching durations in schools. This strategy can enhance students' understanding and retention of complex subjects like Biology.
2. **Monitor and Evaluate Progress:** Continuous monitoring and evaluation of the impact of extended teaching durations are essential. Regular assessments can help track students' progress and identify areas that need improvement. Additionally, gathering feedback from both teachers and students can provide valuable insights for refining the implementation process and maximizing its benefits.

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